

$[\text{Ru(III)}]_{\text{T}} = \{[\text{Ru(III)(OH)}]^{2+} + [\text{Complex } C_1]\}$ the rate law obtained is

$$-\frac{d[\text{Fey}]}{dt} = \frac{2kK[\text{Ru(III)}]_{\text{T}}[\text{S}]}{[\text{OH}^-] + K[\text{S}]} \quad (2)$$

The rate law (?) apparently explains the experimental findings, i.e., first order kinetics with respect to catalyst, first order at lower alcohol and the retarding trend at higher alcohol concentration and the retarding trend due to hydroxide ion concentration.

At higher hydroxide ion and low alcohol concentrations the inequality $[\text{OH}^-] \gg K[\text{S}]$ holds good and equation (2) reduces to

$$-\frac{d[\text{Fe(CN)}_6]^{3-}}{dt} = \frac{2kK[\text{Ru(III)}]_{\text{T}}[\text{S}]}{[\text{OH}^-]} \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

This clearly explains the inverse proportionality due to hydroxide ion and direct proportionality at lower alcohol concentrations. The value of kK at lower alcohol concentration was calculated as 17.5 min^{-1} .

In order to verify the rate law (2) for intermediate concentration of alcohol, the rate equation might be written as

$$\frac{1}{V_1} = \frac{[\text{OH}^-]}{2kK[\text{Ru(III)}]_{\text{T}}[\text{S}]} + \frac{1}{2k[\text{Ru(III)}]_{\text{T}}}$$

where, $V_1 = \frac{-d[\text{Fe(CN)}_6]^{3-}}{dt}$

A plot of $1/\text{Rate}$ vs $[\text{OH}^-]$ gives a straight line with positive intercept supporting the validity of the rate law.

A plot of $\frac{1}{V_1}$ vs $1/[\text{S}]$ gives a straight line with positive intercept on the $\frac{1}{V_1}$ axis. From the slope of straight line the value of kK was calculated and it was found to be 15.5 min^{-1} which is close to the value of kK obtained by equation (3). This is in agreement with the validity of the rate law (2) and supports the proposed reaction mechanism.

Stoichiometry and product study: The number of moles of hexacyanoferrate(III) ion consumed by one mole of benzyl alcohol was determined by taking a number of reaction mixtures in which the concentration of hexacyanoferrate(III) ion was kept ten times larger than benzyl alcohol concentration. After completion of the reaction, the remaining hexacyanoferrate(III) ion was estimated in different sets of experiment. In each set it was found that one mole of alcohol required 2 moles of hexacyanoferrate(III) ion. We, therefore, conclude that the final oxidation product would be benzaldehyde. The reaction mixture was distilled after completion of the reaction and the distillate collected at 177° gave a positive test with Schiff's reagent. On oxidation with alkaline potassium permanganate and further acidification by hydrochloric acid a white precipitate of benzoic acid formed which confirms that the final reaction product is benzaldehyde.

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Non-aqueous Oxidimetric Determination of Phenylhydrazides with Copper(II) in Acetonitrile

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COPPER(II) (in acetonitrile) is an excellent oxidant for use in redox titrations in acetonitrile medium¹. The oxidant possesses high redox potential, suitable stability and the ability to oxidise several compounds¹. Verma *et al* used this oxidant successfully for the determination of xanthates², organotrithiocarbonates³, ascorbic acid⁴, mercaptans⁴ and mercaptopyrimidines⁵ in acetonitrile medium. The use of copper(II) in acetonitrile has now been extended to the determination of phenylhydrazides. These compounds find important applications in medicine, agriculture, industry and in synthetic and analytical chemistry. The determination of these compounds is therefore of great interest and scope. Since these compounds are insoluble in water, the application of non-aqueous redox methods to their determination is advantageous. Most satisfactory results are obtained if copper(II) is titrated with the phenylhydrazide to be determined. Diphenylamine and diphenylbenzidine have been found suitable indicators in visual titrations. The initial blue colour changes to yellow at the end-point. The potentiometric titrations have been performed using an antimony or modified-calomel electrode as reference electrode and a bright platinum wire as indicator electrode. Phenylhydrazides are smoothly, rapidly and quantitatively oxidised with a two-electron change per

TABLE I—DETERMINATION OF PHENYLHYDRAZIDES WITH COPPER(II) IN ACETONITRILE

Phenylhydrazides	Values are mean of ten determinations with standard deviation (\pm)			
	Amount found*, mg		Amount found**, mg	
	Visual method	Potentiometric method	Visual method	Potentiometric method
Formic acid phenylhydrazide	4.04, 0.038	4.03, 0.032	9.97, 0.062	9.98, 0.058
Acetic acid phenylhydrazide	3.95, 0.031	3.98, 0.029	10.08, 0.063	10.06, 0.051
<i>n</i> -Propionic acid phenylhydrazide	3.96, 0.037	3.97, 0.035	9.93, 0.058	9.95, 0.056
Isobutyric acid phenylhydrazide	3.95, 0.036	3.97, 0.032	10.07, 0.058	10.06, 0.043
Benzoic acid phenylhydrazide	4.04, 0.029	—	9.94, 0.061	—
Succinic acid diphenylhydrazide	3.97, 0.030	4.02, 0.030	10.07, 0.049	10.05, 0.048
Adipic acid diphenylhydrazide	4.05, 0.031	4.03, 0.025	10.04, 0.053	9.97, 0.048
Sebacic acid diphenylhydrazide	4.01, 0.039	—	9.93, 0.048	—

* Amount corresponding to theoretical end-point, 4 mg.

** Amount corresponding to theoretical end-point, 10 mg.

hydrazino group. The method is simple, fast, accurate and reliable and seems to have a wide applicability.

Experimental

Apparatus and reagents: Potentiometric titrations were performed with a Toshniwal-CL06A potentiometer, with a bright platinum wire as indicator electrode and a modified-calomel (saturated methanolic potassium chloride instead of aqueous) or antimony electrode as reference electrode.

Acetonitrile: Distilled twice from phosphorus pentoxide (5 g/l).

Hydrated copper(II) perchlorate, 0.04N in acetonitrile: was prepared and standardised as described earlier³.

Carboxylic acid phenylhydrazides: were prepared and purified by the method of Stempel and Schaffel⁴. For preparing their solutions of known strength, phenylhydrazides (from monocarboxylic acids) were dissolved directly in acetonitrile. In case of diphenylhydrazides, a known weight of the compound was dissolved in minimum quantity of acetic acid and the solution diluted with acetonitrile to a known volume.

Indicator solution: Diphenylamine and diphenylhydrazine solution in acetonitrile, 0.1% and 0.05% respectively.

Procedure: Known volumes of standard solutions of copper(II) were taken in dry titration vessels and diluted with 20-30 ml of acetonitrile. For visual titrations, 2-3 drops of indicator solution were also added. Each solution was titrated at room temperature ($\sim 25^\circ$) with the phenylhydrazide (to be determined) solution. The end-point was marked by a sharp colour-change from blue to yellow using either indicator. A series of potentiometric titrations was performed with solutions containing different amounts of each compound using platinum-modified calomel as well as platinum-antimony electrode assembly. The potentiometric titration curves, for one of the listed phenylhydrazides (acetic acid phenylhydrazide) as typical

of the set, using platinum-antimony electrode and platinum-modified calomel electrode assembly are shown in Figs. 1a and 1b respectively. Since the results obtained by potentiometric titrations using

Fig. 1

platinum-modified calomel electrode assembly agree closely with those obtained by using platinum-antimony electrode assembly, only the former are recorded in Table I.

Results and Discussion

Carboxylic acid hydrazides are very important compounds⁷. They find considerable use in chemotherapy. Some hydrazides have been employed as fungicides and plant growth regulators. They are also used as heat and corrosion stabilization of cellulose and its derivatives⁸ and as antioxidants for polyolefins and polyurethanes. Some important ion exchange resins have also been prepared from hydrazides⁹. Acid hydrazides also serve as the starting materials and intermediates in the synthesis of certain amines, aldehydes and heterocyclic compounds that are otherwise difficult to prepare. In

view of the numerous applications of acid hydrazides, their determination is of immense scope and value.

Since the choice of indicator solution did not affect the results of the visual titrations, for brevity only one set of results (with diphenylamine) is recorded in Table 1. In potentiometric titrations, a sharp drop in potential of the order of 180-290 mV per 0.05 ml of the hydrazide solution is observed at the equivalence point when modified-calomel electrode is used and 200-280 mV with the antimony reference electrode. The potentials at the inflection points are 980-590 mV (modified calomel) and 660-380 mV (antimony electrode). The results recorded in Table 1 show that the overall standard deviation calculated from the pooled data of all the visual and potentiometric (modified-calomel electrode) titrations performed with 4 mg (the amount corresponds to the theoretical end-point) of each compound are 0.034 and 0.030 respectively. For 10 mg samples they are 0.056 and 0.052 respectively.

The proposed method is based on the oxidation of phenylhydrazides with a two-electron change per hydrazino group. This may correspond to their oxidation to diazonium compounds.

That phenylhydrazides could be oxidatively converted to diazonium compounds is already known⁷.

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Complexes of Cerium(III) with Benzoic Acid, Protocatechuic Acid and Salicylic Acid : A Polarographic Study

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IN previous communications the complexes of Pr(III) and Nd(III)^{1,2} with benzoic acid, protocatechuic acid and salicylic acid by polarographic technique were reported^{1,2}. However, the literature

is silent about the study of complexes of Ce(III) with these ligands at a DME. The present paper deals with the composition and stability constants of Ce(III) with benzoic acid, protocatechuic acid and salicylic acid respectively by Lingane and Deford-Hume treatment of the observed polarographic data.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR/BDH grade. Ce(III) (0.01 M) solution was prepared by dissolving a calculated quantity of $CeCl_3 \cdot 6H_2O$ (Fluka AG, Switzerland) in conductivity water and was standardised by EDTA method³. Potassium chloride and gelatin solutions were prepared in double distilled water. The stock solutions (0.1 M) of sodium benzoate, protocatechuic acid and potassium salicylate were prepared in carbon-dioxide-free double distilled water.

A preliminary experimental set was prepared by keeping overall concentrations of metal ion, potassium chloride and gelatin at 1 mM, 1.0 M and 0.01 % respectively. While in other sets in addition to the above metal ion, supporting electrolyte and maximum suppressor, the concentration of ligand in each case was varied from 0.25 mM to 30.0 mM. The ionic strength was fixed at $I=1.0$ by adding requisite amount of potassium chloride. The pH of the test solutions was kept at 3.0 ± 0.02 by necessary addition of hydrochloric acid and was measured with an Elico digital pH meter (Model LI-120).

An automatic pen recording polarograph CIC (Baroda, India) was used for recording polarograms. Potentials were measured against saturated calomel electrode. The capillary had the following characteristics; $m=2.13$ mg/sec, $t=3.0$ sec/drop ($m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.323$ mg^{2/3} sec^{-1/6}) in 1.0 M potassium chloride at 35 cm effective height of the mercury column. Pure nitrogen gas was passed through the test solutions before recording the polarograms. All the measurements were made at room temperature, $26 \pm 1^\circ$.

Results and Discussion

Ce(III) gives a well defined, reversible three electron reduction wave in 1.0 M potassium chloride in presence of 0.01% gelatin at pH $3.0 \pm 0.02^{4,5}$. The reduction of Ce(III) and of its complexes with all the three ligands under study were found to be diffusion controlled as the plots of i_d vs \sqrt{t} yielded straight lines passing through the origin. For each polarogram the average value of log plot slope was found to be 20 ± 1 mV indicating reversibility of the electrode process involving three-electron reduction.

Effect of ligand concentration: The half wave potential of Ce(III) shifted to more negative values on gradual increase of the concentration of the ligands under study. The plots of $-E_{1/2}$ against $\log C_x$ (logarithm of the concentration of the ligands)